

Chemical treatments of jute stick for industrial application – A review

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Manuscript received 10 August 2011, revised 07 March 2012, accepted 14 March 2012

Abstract : The chemical analysis of jute stick reveals that it could be a good source of cellulose, active charcoal and furfural with much industrial importance. Cellulose, being the basis of rayon, paper pulp and furfural, is becoming increasingly important due to its application in the plastic industry. The review article describes the use of this lingo-cellulosic raw material for the manufacture of pulp for paper, active charcoals, fillers, etc.

Keywords : Jute stick, carbonization, pulp, paper, furfural, rayon.

Introduction

Jute, the “Golden fibre” has been an important cash crop for the cultivators of the eastern zone of India and is also a valuable exchange earner for the country. Jute stick is a pale coloured, highly porous hence very light and voluminous, woody structure of the jute plant around which the fibres form skin or the bark. The estimated amount of jute stick available in India per annum is about 3 million tones¹. Most of it is used for domestic purposes as fuel, temporary fencing, etc., whereas, a small fraction of it is used industrially^{2,3}.

Chemically jute stick is a lingo-cellulosic raw material⁴⁻⁶. The chemical composition of jute stick is given (Table 1)⁴.

Table 1. Chemical composition of jute stick

Component	Percentage (%)
H ₁₀ O cellulose	72.70
Alpha cellulose	40.80
Pentosans	22.10
Lignin	23.50
Extractives	1.90
Ash	1.00

Production of charcoal :

Jute stick has a chemical composition (with respect to cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin content) close to that of hardwoods. Experiments carried out at NIRJAFT (National Institute of Research on Jute & Allied Fibre Techno-

logy), Kolkata, have indicated that carbonization of jute stick, when carried out under a limited supply of air in a closed container, resulted in the formation of grayish black charcoal at 30–35% yield on dry basis⁷. The ash content of jute stick charcoal has also been found to be significantly lower than that of hardwood charcoal.

Production and properties of jute stick charcoals are mentioned (Table 2)⁸.

Production of activated carbon :

One of the major applications of jute stick in industrial sector would be the production of high grade charcoal by low temperature carbonization process⁸.

The char derived from the pyrolysis of jute stick for bio-oil production was used to produce activated carbon⁹. The activated carbons produced were characterized by measuring BET surface area, iodine number, carbon tetrachloride adsorption and benzene adsorption. The effects of the activation temperature, steam flow rate and adsorption time on yield and properties of activated carbon are mentioned (Tables 3 to 5)⁹.

Effect of activation temperature :

The effect of temperature on the yield and properties of activated carbon is given (Table 3)⁹. The activation burn-off was a function of temperature and the higher the temperature, the higher was the activation burn-off. Thus the yield of activated carbon decreased with the increase of temperature.

Table 2. Production and properties of jute stick charcoals

Source	Carbonization temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Fixed carbon (%)	Ash (%)	Possible application
Jute stick in chip form	300	35-40	75	3-4	In smokeless fuel consumption
Jute stick in pressed form	350	35	80	3-4	In smokeless fuel consumption
Pretreated jute stick chips (water digestion at 14 °C for 1 h)	400-450	28	90	2-3	As source of chemical carbon in CS ₂ manufacture and to enrich low quality cake
Two-stage carbonization	400-450	33	90	3-4	As source of chemical carbon in CS ₂ manufacture and to enrich low quality cake
Hardwood charcoal (high grade)	-	-	88	5-6	Used to manufacture CS ₂ in viscose rayon mills

Table 3. Effect of temperature on the yield and properties of activated carbon

Temp. (°C)	700	750	800	850	900
Water flow rate (mg/min)	75	75	75	75	75
Nitrogen gas flow rate (ml/min)	300	300	300	300	300
Activation time (h)	1	1	1	1	1
Amount of char (g)	10	10	10	10	10
Amount of activated carbon produced (g)	5.83	5.01	2.60	2.12	1.73
Activation burn off (wt%)	41.65	50.05	68.00	78.76	82.70
Yield :					
Activated carbon (wt%)	58.35	49.95	32.00	21.24	17.30
Properties :					
BET surface area (m ² /s)	509	724	605	513	452
Iodine number (mg/g)	338	573	433	362	327

Table 4. Effect of steam flow rate on the yield and properties of activated carbon

Steam flow rate (mg/min)	75	150	300	600	1125
Temp. (°C)	750	750	750	750	750
Nitrogen gas flow rate (ml/min)	300	300	300	300	300
Activation time (h)	1	1	1	1	1
Amount of char (g)	10	10	10	10	10
Amount of activation carbon produced (g)	5.01	4.53	2.26	1.46	0.95
Activation burn off (wt%)	50.05	44.68	77.38	85.47	90.49
Yield :					
Activated carbon (wt%)	49.95	45.32	22.62	14.57	9.51
Properties :					
BET surface area (m ² /s)	724	601	560	425	360
Iodine number (mg/g)	573	340	310	285	255

Table 5. Effect of adsorption time on the amount of carbon tetrachloride and benzene adsorption

Adsorption time (min)	Carbon tetrachloride adsorption (mg/g)		Benzene adsorption (mg/g)	
	Commercial	Experimental	Commercial	Experimental
	sample	sample	sample	sample
5	4.57	4.61	5.48	5.69
10	7.18	9.13	7.38	11.58
15	10.02	12.20	10.87	15.97
20	12.40	16.57	13.09	23.36
25	15.73	26.15	16.33	27.00
30	17.74	36.48	20.20	32.59
45	24.50	47.78	26.94	42.43
60	30.51	51.50	32.32	49.50
120	30.50	51.80	32.43	48.90
180	30.63	52.00	32.63	49.10

Table 6. Effect of variations in the concentration of the cooking liquor on yield of pulp

Cooking liquor		Liquor to goods ratio (on air-dry basis)	Unbleached pulp yield, % (on oven dry basis)	Strength properties					
Na ₂ SO ₃ (g/L)	Na ₂ CO ₃ (g/L)			Paper sheets			Boards		
				Basis wt. (g/m ²)	Burst factor	Breaking length (m)	Basis wt. (g/m ²)	Burst factor	Breaking length (m)
8	2.0	10 : 1	72.2	38.0	23.2	4978	407.0	22.2	5714
10	2.5	10 : 1	70.6	38.4	18.3	3989	372.0	25.6	5390
12	3.0	10 : 1	70.2	40.3	30.6	5080	432.0	32.1	7555
15	3.75	8 : 1	70.6	43.8	26.2	5804	458.5	27.5	6288
16	4.0	10 : 1	69.9	36.2	23.0	5175	424.5	33.0	7041

Table 7. Percentages of pentosans, furfural in some agricultural wastes

Material	Pentosans	Furfural
Corn cobs	30.27	17.76
Coconut shells	27.60	16.20
Bagasse	26.29	15.51
Bagasse pith	24.62	14.02
Jute stick	22.10	12.15
Maize stem pith	20.05	11.77
Rice husk	16.94	9.82
Peanut shells	16.70	9.45
Coffee bean shells	15.85	10.28
Cocoa husks	15.40	9.00
Cotton seed hulls	13.00	8.81

Effect of steam flow rate :

The yield of activated carbon greatly varied with varying steam flow rate is given (Table 4)⁹. The activation burn-off of char takes place through the steam reforming

reaction of char which is faster in the presence of greater availability of steam and thus the yield of activated carbon is decreased with increasing steam flow rate.

Effect of adsorption time :

The carbon tetrachloride adsorption on commercial and experimental activated carbons at different adsorption times is given (Table 5)⁹. Both commercial and experimental activated carbons exhibited increased adsorption of carbon tetrachloride with increasing time.

Production of board and cheap grade paper by neutral sulphite semi-chemical process :

Jute stick, the by product of jute crop can play an important role for the development of pulp and paper industries¹⁰⁻¹⁶. Information on pulping of jute sticks with lime¹⁷ and with nitric acid¹⁸ was available.

The neutral sulphite semi-chemical (N.S.S.C.) process was used for pulping of jute sticks. The chips were

given a mild digestion for a period of four hours at a pressure 65 lb/in². A sprout Waldron Laboratory Refiner was used for refining the partially digested chips at a consistency of about three percent¹⁹. The colour of the paper sheets and boards (both hand made) was whitish grey, and their formation was quite satisfactory. The results are shown (Table 6)¹⁹.

Table 6 shows that the variations in the concentration of the cooking liquor do not materially affect the yield of the pulp. The strength properties of the boards appear suitable for cigarette cartons, but some improvement in tearing resistance is yet desirable. Thin cards of approximately the same basic weight as that of the post cards were also made. They appear satisfactory in all respects except the shade.

Production of pulp by sulphate fractional digestion process :

Jute stick on digestion with overhead soda and sulphate process using 3.5% alkali (total alkali being 35%) yielded about 47% and 42% unbleached and bleached pulps, respectively. The chemical consumption was about 27% on oven dry jute stick²⁰.

Fractional digestion method, i.e. two stage digestion process was carried out with sulphate liquor (Na₂S : NaOH 1 : 3)²¹.

In the first stage of digestion, the jute stick chips were digested with the black liquor of the previous cook. The ratio of the chips to black liquor was 1 : 10 and the total chemicals were 9–10% NaOH on oven dry basis of jute stick. The digestion was carried out for 2 h at 125–130 °C. After the digestion was completed, the black liquor was drained out and the semi cooked charge was kept for the second stage digestion. With this preliminary digestion, constituents soluble in dilute alkali were dissolved out whereas, lignin and other binding materials resistant to 1% alkali remained in the stick.

In the second stage of digestion, the strength of the cooking liquor was 6.0% and the total chemicals were 26–27% on the basis of woven dry jute stick. Digestions were carried out at 153 °C for 3–4 h. After the digestion was over, the black liquor was collected for the preliminary digestion of the following cook. The unbleached pulp was washed and then bleached in two stages with an intermediate alkali wash. The unbleached and bleached

pulp yields were found to be 46.0% and 43.3% respectively. The chemicals consumption was about 25.0% on oven dry jute sticks.

It was observed that with the fractional digestion method the yield of the unbleached pulp was slightly lower than that obtained with overhead method, however, the yield of the bleached pulp was slightly higher. The advantages of fractional digestion process over single stage digestion process are as follows :

- (i) Pulp was more homogenous.
- (ii) Unbleached pulp was much lighter in shade and was easily bleachable.
- (iii) The alkali to jute stick ratio is low.
- (iv) The alkali consumption was low.

Jute stick for production of furfural :

Jute stick was utilized for the preparation of furfural and was observed that 9.7% furfural could be recovered from jute stick by direct distillation using sulphuric acid²².

Successful isolation of pure furfural was done through the reaction carried out with catalytic amount of cheap sulphuric acid preferably under pressure⁴.

The characterization of furfural by the colour reaction with aniline acetate solution and orcinol-ferric chloride reagent was done²³. The purity of the product was further ascertained by Gas Liquid Chromatography. A Hewlett Packard gas chromatograph (model 5830A) with flame detector was used. Resolution was achieved in a stainless steel column (1.5 × 0.05 cm) containing 30% OV-225 on Superlocopot Q (80–100 mesh) at 443 K, with nitrogen as carrier gas. The rate of flow was 20 cm³ min⁻¹. The injection temperature was 523 K. The isolated furfural was found to be 99.5% pure with no contamination of hydroxymethyl furfural.

The comparison of percentage of pentosans and furfural in different agro-residues is shown (Table 7)⁴.

Jute stick flour as filler :

With the growth of the plastic industry the demand for wood flour is increasing day by day. Wood flours are used as fillers in various types of moulding powders. The proportion and quality of wood flour added depends upon type of resin used, however, in some cases wood flours are added up to 50% of the total bulk. These fillers are

used mainly to reduce the overall cost and they also serve as a convenient base for colour effects²⁴.

The flour obtained from jute stick proved to be a good substitute for imported wood flour²⁵. Jute sticks were cut into small chips and were soaked in water for 24 h, then dried, crushed and powered in a hammer mill disintegrator. The fine powder passing through 200 mesh sieve was used as filler. The maximum yield of filler was obtained in the range of 50–52% on oven dry basis.

Production of rayon grade pulp :

A process for preparation of rayon grade pulp from jute stick has been developed in National Institute of Research on Jute and Allied Fibre Technology, Kolkata^{26,27}. It was found that high tenacity tyre cord type of yarn and rayon staple fibre can be manufactured from such pulp. Ordinary viscose can also be prepared from such pulp and the technology of processing of jute stick depends on the quality of the products required.

Conclusion :

Jute stick, considered as an agricultural waste, can be used as a raw material for number of ancillary industries. It can be utilized in the manufacture of pulp, furfural, activated carbon, filler materials etc., organized efforts in this direction can benefit the farmer with better price of their crop and employment opportunities in rural sectors.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Dr. K. K. Satapathy, Director, National Institute of Research on Jute and Allied Fibre Technology, Kolkata for his constant encouragement.

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